

THE LEGAL NATURE OF PRESIDENTIAL DECREES REGULATING COOPERATION BETWEEN INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES AND SELF-GOVERNING BODIES

Mehmonali Suvankulov

Head of the Department of Legal Sciences, Institute for Advanced
Training of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of
Uzbekistan, Candidate of Juridical Sciences, Professor
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Abstract. This article analyzes the legal framework for cooperation between internal affairs bodies and the mahalla institution, examining Presidential decrees classified according to their content. The decrees outline provisions aimed at ensuring public safety, improving the system of preventive measures, and developing mechanisms for cooperation with the mahalla. The article also substantiates that the effectiveness of this cooperation has increased through the introduction of the "mahalla seven" institution and the implementation of digital technologies.

Keywords: Presidential decrees, classification, internal affairs bodies, mahalla, public safety, preventive measures, cooperation.

Cooperation between internal affairs bodies and citizens' self-governing bodies (the mahalla institution) is one of the most important aspects of the public safety system. Regulatory legal acts adopted in recent years aim to elevate this cooperation to a new level, improve preventive work, and create a stable and safe environment in mahallas.

Today, the mahalla institution, not just law enforcement agencies, participates as a key entity in crime prevention and stabilizing the criminogenic situation. The implementation of digital technologies, a targeted approach, and the "mahalla seven" mechanism makes enhancing the effectiveness of this cooperation a pressing task.

Based on the norms of the new edition of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the system for the legal regulation of cooperation between internal affairs bodies and citizens' self-governing bodies is being improved. This process is implemented through subordinate regulatory legal acts, which serve to increase practical effectiveness.

According to their legal force, these documents are studied by dividing them into presidential decrees, presidential resolutions, resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers, and interdepartmental documents.

Analysis shows that the President's regulatory legal acts play a key role in developing cooperation between internal affairs bodies and the mahalla institution and are aimed at eliminating existing legal gaps.

Presidential decrees are conventionally divided into three groups: a) those of a general societal nature; b) those pertaining to internal affairs bodies;

c) and documents related to the activities of mahalla bodies.

Overall, these legal mechanisms serve to strengthen the cooperation between the two systems and increase its efficiency.

The Presidential Decree, adopted within the framework of the Development Strategy, aims to increase the efficiency of internal affairs bodies and strengthen their responsibility for protecting public order and the rights and legitimate interests of citizens. It notes existing

problems in cooperation between internal affairs bodies and citizens' self-government bodies and defines new organizational and legal mechanisms for their elimination[2].

In particular, it emphasizes the need to improve the communication culture of internal affairs officers with the population and to establish effective cooperation between prevention inspectors and civil society institutions. Furthermore, strengthening systemic dialogue with citizens' assemblies and other public structures in solving public problems has been identified as a priority of the reforms.

In order to ensure the implementation of the decree, a reporting system has been implemented at all levels to ensure public safety. According to it, prevention inspectors submit reports on their activities to the mahalla authorities, and the citizens' assembly discusses these reports. This mechanism serves to strengthen interaction and public control between internal affairs bodies and the mahalla system.

According to the presidential decree, it is planned to bring the activities of internal affairs bodies to a new level, introduce a systematic approach to ensuring public safety and combating crime. It defines one of the main directions as increasing the effectiveness of prevention by identifying the causes of offenses in the context of the mahalla, family, and individual, as well as eliminating them on the spot.

It also provides for the categorization of districts, cities, and mahallas based on the criminogenic situation in the regions and the strengthening of cooperation between state bodies and the public in eliminating "hotspots of crime." In addition, a unified management and continuous control system based on the "republic - region - district - mahalla" principle has been introduced, and it is planned to strengthen interdepartmental coordination in ensuring public safety [5].

These mechanisms serve to strengthen cooperation between internal affairs bodies and citizens' self-government bodies, as well as to increase the efficiency of ensuring public safety.

In accordance with this decree, mahalla law enforcement centers were gradually established based on the strongpoints of the internal affairs bodies. They function as the lower level for ensuring public safety, preventing offenses, and combating crime.

At the same time, the activities of the sectoral services of the internal affairs bodies, the National Guard, and other state bodies have been organized within these centers in a coordinated manner. Ensuring public safety and the systematic management of preventive work are the responsibility of prevention inspectors.

This system contributes to the development of cooperation with citizens' self-government bodies based on new organizational and practical forms and methods.

The Concept of Public Safety of the Republic of Uzbekistan identifies cooperation between state and public institutions as a priority in improving the public safety system. It recognizes the active participation of citizens' self-government bodies, non-governmental non-profit organizations, and the media in socio-political processes as an important factor in ensuring public safety.

According to the concept, ensuring public safety is carried out in cooperation with civil society institutions alongside state bodies. It is also envisaged that the mahalla system will participate in the implementation of state programs and exercise public control over legislation in the field of public safety.

Furthermore, the direct participation of citizens' self-government bodies and non-governmental non-profit organizations in processes by assisting entities ensuring public safety

is legally enshrined. These rules serve to bring cooperation between the internal affairs bodies and the mahalla system to a new level.

In accordance with the Strategy for the Development of the Public Safety System in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2025, a new institutional mechanism for ensuring public safety at the mahalla level has been formed. According to the document, one mahalla law enforcement post has been established for each of the five mahallas based on a standard project, serving as the primary prevention center at the lower level.

Additionally, a system of joint activities between internal affairs bodies, other law enforcement agencies, and public structures has been established in these centers. Infrastructure for road safety training has been established in educational institutions and mahallas, and the scope of preventive and educational work has been expanded.

Furthermore, an effective system for coordinating the activities of public order units of the National Guard and internal affairs bodies, as well as "Fidokor Yoshlar" public patrol groups, has been introduced. At the same time, integrated mechanisms aimed at working with unorganized youth have been formed between internal affairs bodies and state and public organizations working with youth.

These reforms contribute to the development of new, systematic, and effective forms of cooperation between internal affairs bodies and citizens' self-government bodies in ensuring public safety.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-5938 dated February 18, 2020, serves as an important legal basis for improving the activities of the mahalla institution and citizens' self-government bodies, as well as for bringing their cooperation with internal affairs bodies to a new level. This document defines comprehensive reforms aimed at increasing the role and status of the mahalla institution in society, as well as improving the socio-spiritual environment.

In accordance with the decree, legal guarantees are established, such as preventing unjustified interference by state bodies in the activities of citizens' self-government bodies, creating the necessary conditions for their effective functioning, and providing practical assistance in exercising their powers[10].

It also provides for the introduction of mechanisms for close cooperation between the mahalla institution and the population, increasing women's activity, ensuring socio-spiritual stability, and continuous interaction with internal affairs bodies based on the "Prosperous and Safe Mahalla" principle. Particular attention is paid to strengthening the role and responsibility of prevention inspectors and mahalla workers, introducing modern information technologies into their activities, and improving their material and technical base.

As a result of these reforms, the system of cooperation between the mahalla institution and internal affairs bodies has reached a qualitatively new level [11].

Furthermore, internal affairs bodies and citizens' self-government bodies also cooperate within the framework of implementing Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-5712 dated April 29, 2019, "On Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Public Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030," and No. UP-5863 dated October 30, 2019, "On Approval of the Concept for Environmental Protection for the Period until 2030."

This cooperation is organized within the powers established by current legislation and serves to increase public participation and the role of the mahalla institution in the

implementation of state policy aimed at developing the education system and ensuring environmental sustainability.

Cooperation between internal affairs bodies and citizens' self-government bodies (the mahalla institution) is one of the main directions of the public security system in Uzbekistan. Presidential resolutions adopted in recent years, including Resolution No. PP-1 dated January 3, 2025, "On measures to create a safe environment and further increase the efficiency of the early crime prevention system in the mahallas of the republic in 2025," also define bringing this cooperation to a new level, stabilizing the criminogenic situation, and forming an effective system for early crime prevention as a priority task.

In accordance with this resolution, a completely new organizational, legal, and practical mechanism for ensuring a safe environment in the mahalla has been formed between the internal affairs bodies and the "mahalla seven." The main essence of this mechanism is the introduction of a comprehensive approach to ensuring public safety, not only by the activities of law enforcement agencies, but also by uniting all responsible entities at the mahalla level into a single system.

Within the framework of the new system, a continuous exchange of information has been established between the internal affairs bodies and the "mahalla seven," and the practice of constant monitoring of the socio-legal situation in each mahalla, joint planning and implementation of targeted preventive measures aimed at identifying and eliminating criminogenic factors has been formed. This will ensure a systematic approach to the early prevention of crime.

Furthermore, this mechanism clearly defines the tasks and responsibilities of each entity; while internal affairs bodies are primarily responsible for law enforcement, the implementation of operational-preventive measures, and ensuring public order, the "mahalla seven" performs tasks such as direct work with the population, identifying social problems, resolving family and domestic conflicts at an early stage, and ensuring public oversight.

Furthermore, this cooperation system is aimed at strengthening responsibility at the mahalla level, introducing clear personal and institutional responsibility for the criminogenic situation in each region. This ensures that work is organized not in a sluggish manner, but in a manner aimed at a specific result.

Overall, this new cooperation mechanism between internal affairs bodies and the "mahalla seven" has radically improved the public safety system, contributing to increasing the effectiveness of preventive work, strengthening close dialogue with the population, and creating a stable safe environment in mahallas.

In accordance with Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-1 dated January 5, 2026, "On additional measures aimed at implementing a holistic targeted work system to create a safe environment in the mahallas of the republic," the system of cooperation between internal affairs bodies and the mahalla seven has been elevated to a new level and is being formed as a targeted and comprehensive mechanism for ensuring a safe environment in mahallas. The main goal of this approach is the early prevention of crime, the systematic elimination of criminogenic factors, and the organization of preventive work in close cooperation with the population.

According to the resolution, internal affairs bodies will organize targeted preventive work by analyzing the regional criminogenic situation, identifying risk groups, and identifying mahallas in the "red" category. Based on this information, the "mahalla seven" works directly

with the population and carries out individual preventive measures with families, youth, and persons with social problems.

The "Social Prevention Week" system was introduced as an important form of cooperation, during which internal affairs bodies generate analysis and information, while the "mahalla seven" carries out work to solve problems and provide social support on the ground. Thus, the mechanisms of prevention and social work are harmonized.

Additionally, digital systems such as "E-social prevention" automate data exchange and analysis processes, increasing the efficiency of cooperation. The resolution also introduces a personal responsibility and result-based evaluation system, where the performance of each responsible official will be evaluated based on specific indicators.

Overall, this decision transformed cooperation between the internal affairs bodies and the mahalla seven into a unified system focused on prevention, targeted, and based on digital technologies. This will serve to ensure a safe environment in mahallas and reduce crime.

Conclusions and suggestions. The conducted analysis shows that the system of cooperation between internal affairs bodies and citizens' self-government bodies (the mahalla institution) has been consistently improving institutionally and functionally in recent years. This process is formed on the basis of constitutional reforms, presidential decrees and resolutions, and sectoral strategies, ensuring the transition to a new - preventive-oriented, targeted, and digitalized model of ensuring public safety.

In particular, the introduction of the "mahalla seven" institution at the mahalla level and its close integration with internal affairs bodies serves as an effective legal and organizational mechanism for early crime prevention, systematic analysis of criminogenic factors, and the implementation of social prevention. This contributes to the institutionalization of mutual responsibility between the state and society in ensuring public safety.

At the same time, in practical processes, issues such as the uneven distribution of resources across regions, the incomplete integration of digital systems, and the lack of continuity in information exchange between prevention entities are identified.

First and foremost, in order to further strengthen legal cooperation between internal affairs bodies and the mahalla institution, it is advisable to develop a unified comprehensive regulatory legal act "On Public Safety and Preventive Cooperation." This document must clearly and systematically define the powers, responsibilities, and mutual integration mechanisms of the subjects.

Second, it is necessary to fully automate prevention processes, analyze data in real time, and accelerate the decision-making system by integrating E-social prevention and other information systems into a single digital platform.

Thirdly, in order to increase the professional potential of prevention entities at the mahalla level, it is advisable to introduce unified educational and methodological standards and a system of regular professional development for internal affairs officers and the mahalla "seven."

Fourth, it is necessary to improve the result-oriented evaluation system, that is, to include not only statistical indicators, but also indicators of real crime reduction, public satisfaction and social stability in the KPI system.

Overall, a sustainable, effective, and modern model for ensuring public safety can be formed through the further institutionalization and digitalization of cooperation between internal affairs bodies and the mahalla institution

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